

ISic2726

I.Sicily inscription 2726

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euonymus

Place of origin (modern)

Panarea

Provenance

Found in localita San Pietro (east coast of island), in 1975 (work near Hotel Raya)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334613

1. Φέρου-
2. σα, χαῖ-
3. ρε.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645146

EDCS 71000722

PHI 334613

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1389

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 509

Giustolisi, V. 1995. Vulcano. Introduzione alla storia e all'archeologia dell'antica Hiera. Palermo. At 15

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2726. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387311>